

The PISA Tests at a Global Level

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The PISA scales in reading, mathematics, and science refer to the scores achieved by students in the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) tests, an initiative of the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). PISA assesses the skills of 15-year-old students in three main areas: reading, mathematics, and science. The goal is to measure students' ability to apply their knowledge in real-world contexts, rather than simply evaluating their recall of school-taught information. The reading scale measures students' ability to understand, use, and reflect on written texts in order to achieve personal goals, develop their knowledge, and effectively participate in society. Students are assessed on their ability to interpret various types of texts and analyze complex information. The mathematics scale evaluates students' ability to formulate, use, and interpret mathematics in a range of contexts. This includes the ability to recognize the role mathematics plays in the real world, make deductions, and apply mathematical knowledge to solve practical problems. The science scale, on the other hand, measures students' ability to explain scientific phenomena, interpret scientific data, and apply scientific reasoning to solve problems. The focus is on their ability to understand scientific concepts and use them in practical, everyday contexts. PISA scores are presented on a continuous scale, with an average score around 500 points for each domain. These scores allow for the comparison of student performance at the international level, identifying both areas of excellence and weakness across different educational systems. The PISA scales also help governments formulate educational policies based on objective data. The data covers the period from 2013 to 2022.

PISA Test in 2022. The 2022 data from the PISA (Programme for International Student Assessment) scales, which measure students' competencies in reading, mathematics, and science, show a clear divide between nations with highly developed education systems and those with less advanced educational infrastructures. At the top of the rankings is China, with a perfect score of 100, followed by Singapore (90.8) and Hong Kong SAR (80.3). These results confirm the dominance of East Asian countries, which have heavily invested in education and adopted rigorous pedagogical approaches aimed at developing advanced cognitive skills in their students. China, in particular, places strong emphasis on mathematical and scientific competencies, which are central to its educational curriculum, designed to support an increasingly technology-based and innovation-driven society. Estonia (78.2) is a noteworthy case in Europe, ranking near the top of the global chart and surpassing nations like Japan (75.9) and South Korea (75.8), two education giants in Asia. Estonia achieved this result due to its strong focus on digital inclusion and an innovative school system that promotes critical thinking and student independence. Finland (74.4) and Poland (73) also stand out for their excellent results, confirming that Northern and Eastern Europe continue to provide high-quality education despite the socio-economic challenges some countries face. The United Kingdom (69.1), Ireland (69.6), and Sweden (68.8) also rank highly, indicating that Western Europe continues to maintain high educational standards. However, countries like Germany (67.9) and France (65.1), despite being economic powers, do not achieve outstanding results in this ranking. This could raise questions about the need for reforms in their education systems to address the demands of an increasingly globalized and competitive world. On the other hand, the United States (65.8), despite its global leadership in many sectors, does not rank at the top of the PISA scale. This result reflects a long-standing internal debate in the U.S. regarding inequalities in the education system and the need for overall improvements in public schools, which often show highly variable results depending on region and socio-economic conditions. At the lower end of the rankings are several countries from

Latin America, the Middle East, and Africa. Countries such as Brazil (26.9), Argentina (24.9), and Peru (27.5) clearly show significant difficulties in providing quality education. This can be attributed to structural problems related to poverty, inequality, and a lack of resources dedicated to education. In particular, the extremely low scores of the Philippines (6.4) and North African countries like Tunisia (15.2) and Morocco (13.8) highlight the urgent need for investment in educational infrastructure to improve students' basic competencies. In conclusion, the 2022 PISA data reveals a stark divide between countries with solid education systems and those struggling to provide quality education. The best results come from Asian countries, followed by some European nations, while many regions in Latin America, the Middle East, and Africa face significant challenges. These results reflect not only the quality of educational systems but also the impact of economic, social, and cultural factors on student learning.

PISA Test from 2013 to 2022. The PISA (Programme for International Student Assessment) data from 2013 to 2022 shows significant changes in student performance in reading, mathematics, and science across various countries, highlighting both progress and setbacks in educational outcomes. These changes often reflect the socio-economic reforms and challenges faced by different educational systems. One of the most noticeable trends is the significant improvement in some developing countries. For example, Qatar, Peru, and Albania recorded substantial increases in their PISA scores. Qatar improved by 13.3 points (a 69.63% increase), Peru by 10.4 points (60.82%), and Albania by 11.4 points (48.31%). These increases suggest that these countries have made significant investments in their educational systems, likely through reforms aimed at improving access to quality education, teacher training, and curriculum development. In particular, Qatar's substantial improvement may result from massive investments in educational infrastructure and the promotion of international educational standards. Similarly, the progress made by Peru and Albania likely reflects targeted efforts to address educational inequalities and enhance student performance. Other countries, such as Moldova and Montenegro, have also seen moderate gains, albeit at a slower pace. Moldova increased its PISA scores by 7.3 points (24.66%) and Montenegro by 4.6 points (14.7%). These countries seem to be following a gradual path of improvement, thanks to moderate educational reforms that are beginning to yield positive results. In contrast, Azerbaijan, Jordan, and Georgia registered only minimal increases in their scores, reflecting slower progress. Despite the improvements, their growth rate suggests that these countries may still face significant challenges within their educational systems, such as teacher shortages, outdated curricula, or insufficient funding. On the other hand, many developed countries experienced stagnation or a decline in PISA scores during this period. Countries like the United States, Spain, France, and Norway all saw a drop in educational performance, with the United States losing 2.3 points (3.38%), Spain 2.8 points (4.42%), and France 3.2 points (4.69%). These declines suggest that even advanced economies can struggle to maintain high educational standards, possibly due to policy changes, demographic dynamics, or challenges related to educational equity. The United Kingdom and Canada also recorded small but significant decreases, indicating potential issues within their educational systems despite their relative prosperity and resources. One of the most concerning data points is the significant decline in PISA scores in traditionally high-performing countries such as Finland, New Zealand, Switzerland, and South Korea. Finland saw a drop of 12.4 points (14.29%), New Zealand 10.2 points (12.9%), and South Korea 10 points (11.66%). These declines may be attributed to several factors, including growing educational inequalities, changes in educational policies, or social transformations that impact student engagement and performance. Finland's decline is particularly surprising, given the country's long-standing reputation for educational excellence. This decrease may indicate difficulties in adapting to new educational demands or the impact of external factors, such as student well-being or demographic changes. Countries such as Panama, Tunisia, and Costa Rica registered the sharpest declines in PISA

performance. Tunisia, for example, experienced a dramatic drop of 11.4 points (42.86%), while Panama lost 4.9 points (28.16%). These significant declines highlight the educational challenges faced by many developing nations, exacerbated by political instability, economic difficulties, or a lack of adequate educational resources. In summary, the 2013-2022 PISA data presents a mixed global picture. Some countries, particularly those in the developing world, have shown impressive progress, while many developed nations are struggling with stagnation or declines in student performance. This trend underscores the complexity of the education sector, where continuous investment, adaptability, and attention to policy are crucial for maintaining and improving educational outcomes.

Conclusions. The average PISA test scores decreased from a value of 54.97 units to 52.78 units, representing a reduction of -4.00%. The top performers are: Qatar with +69.63%, Peru with +60.82%, Albania with +48.31%, Moldova with +24.66%, and Montenegro with +14.70%. The worst performers are: Greece with -17.18%, Indonesia with -18.41%, Costa Rica with -18.92%, Panama with -28.16%, and Tunisia with -42.68%.

Database: Global Innovation Index. <https://www.wipo.int/portal/en/> Accessed on 13 October 2024.

Performance	Countries	2013	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Top Performance	Qatar	★ 19	★ 32	★ 13,3	★ 69,63
	Peru	★ 17	★ 28	★ 10,4	★ 60,82
	Albania	★ 24	★ 35	★ 11,4	★ 48,31
	Moldova	★ 30	★ 37	★ 7,3	★ 24,66
	Montenegro	★ 31	★ 36	★ 4,6	★ 14,70
Worse Performance	Greece	★ 59	★ 49	★ -10	★ -17,18
	Indonesia	★ 24	★ 20	★ -4,4	★ -18,41
	Costa Rica	★ 41	★ 33	★ -7,7	★ -18,92
	Panama	★ 17	★ 13	★ -4,9	★ -28,16
	Tunisia	★ 27	★ 15	★ -11	★ -42,86

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